

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Exploring the transcriptional program that instructs remodelling of the branchial arches (BA) in the heart

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

The study will generate Sequencing data, i.e. ChIP-Seq to identify epigenetic modification and RNA-Seq to understand the gene expression. Mouse cell lines from embryos between developmental stages E10.5 and E11.5 generated during the project will be used. Raw data will be saved in the FASTQ format, and processed data will be in the form of images (.svg) and .csv files.

II. Standards and metadata

RNA-Seq and Chip-Seq data will be annotated in compliance with the community metadata standard MINSEQE model (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5706412). In addition, metadata will also comply with the requirements of the public repository, e.g. ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress), in which data will be deposited for reuse and long-term preservation. All details of the software (including versions) used, analysis pipelines will also be described in the methodology described in the associated publication.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Data will be generated using new mice cell lines developed from embryos between developmental stages E10.5 and E11.5 to carry out the ChIP-Seq and RNA-Seq experiments. No existing data will be used.

IV. Secondary use

Data will be freely available for secondary analysis by the research community after its public release, post-publication. New data generated from this study will help researchers better understand the developmental process of heart arteries.

V. Methods for data sharing

All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be available to all via the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress). The images will be available as part of the publication. Array Express assigns a unique identifier to each dataset, called the Accession Number, which can be searched and referenced in future.

VI. Proprietary data

We do not expect to have any restrictions or delays to data sharing. Data will be shared publicly via ArrayExpress immediately after publication.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be shared publicly via ArrayExpress immediately after publication. We do not expect to have any restrictions or delays to data sharing.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Raw data will be saved in the FASTQ format, and processed data will be in the form of images (.svg) and .csv files.